

Fjord Phantom Malware Process and Execution Analysis in Mobile Banking Application

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Abstract—Technological development and acceleration cannot be avoided in the digital era. Technology is used in various transactions to support existing productivity. However, behind it all, some vulnerabilities and risks always arise without users realizing it. One of them is FjordPhantom. Fjordphantom is the name of malware with different characteristics from most malware. This malware is a combination of malware attacks on various banking service applications. The process carried out by the creator of this malware is to embed the software into the virtualization server where the official banking service application is located. The impact is extraordinary and causes the users or customers served to lose quite a lot of material. This research was conducted to provide an overview of this malware in the real world. The author tries to study this by analyzing various information obtained from journals and papers related to the process and execution carried out by the malware on existing banking service applications. The research method used is qualitative, with a research model, namely, a systematic literature review. Based on the results of the analysis and the conclusions obtained, 22 papers discussed this malware.

In contrast, most existing banking service technology and application users are unaware of this malware. The author's hope in writing about the process and execution carried out by this malware is to provide an accurate picture that behind the technology used and used as a reference by its users, it is necessary always to be aware of it and make important notes in its use. Moreover, other malware that is more sophisticated in technology may emerge in the future.

Keywords— *Malware, FjordPhantom, Mobile Banking, Virtual Machine, Android OS*

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's highly developed digital era, using digital devices in everyday life is inevitable. The author often encounters digital devices such as computers, laptops, smartphones, and tablets, both in banking and non-banking, so their use is beneficial and helps us in our activities. However, technology is also often used to carry out criminal activities in cyberspace, usually called cybercrime[1].

There are many types of cybercrime, one of which is often called hacking, where this activity infiltrates or breaks into digital devices used by users so that all data and networks owned can be publicly revealed [2]. It is due to the existence of tools in the form of software designed to damage the

computer system used, which is called malware [3]. Although these two things are different, malware is often used in the hacking process to make it easier to steal data or commit other crimes.

Along with very rapid technological developments, conventional banking services are starting to be abandoned, and customers or users are switching to digital services. By using digital services, transactions can be carried out anywhere and at any time according to the needs of users or customers, thereby increasing the economy. However, this can also be a threat and problem because banking services have been digitized, opening up opportunities for cybercriminals to commit crimes. Moreover, the techniques used to commit crimes are very diverse, ranging from fraud phishing to malware to commit the crime. Therefore, using digital banking services makes the transaction process more accessible and increases the time risk[4].

According to Kaspersky Security Network, during Q2 2023, 5,704,599 Android malware were blocked. Of the total malware that has been blocked, 30.8% is unwanted software. The malware also attacks Android users' mobile banking, as it was discovered in an online store embedded with JavaScript code to steal details from their bank cards.

Android devices have developed over time, increasing vulnerabilities in Android applications. It can happen because it is open source, and this statement is supported by the Quick Heal Quarterly Threat Report Q1, which states that Android malware was developed 304 times between 2011 and 2014. So, it can be concluded that Android is more vulnerable to malware attacks.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Virtualization

Virtualization in computer technology creates a new virtual environment that is not connected to a device's primary environment[5]. The virtualization technique also means separating the computer environment from its physical infrastructure and then dividing it into several virtual machines. It can run several tasks simultaneously on one device[6]. Virtualization can be a double-edged sword

because it can hide malware and, conversely, detect dangerous things or malware[7].

In terms of malware detection, several tools can be used, one of which is Red Pill, but there is no 100% guarantee that this VM detection method will successfully detect malware [8]. The process of detecting malware attacks using a VM will be more difficult because there is no direct access to the physical memory of the VM[9], [10], [11].

Meanwhile, this technique can also threaten computer users by hiding malware. One type of malware that uses VMs is Virtual Machine Based Rookits (VMBR). This type of malware is hazardous because it operates in a virtual environment, so it is tough for the device's security system to detect it [10].

B. Malware

Malware combines the words malicious and software, so malware is used when unwanted software aims to harm or make system functions not work[12]. *Malware* can be divided based on the characteristics of replication, propagation, self-execution, and damage to computer systems, where damage can impact confidential information, integrity, and service[12]. There are several types of malware, such as:

1. Trojans

Trojans are malware applications that appear non-suspicious but steal confidential user information without the user's knowledge[13].

2. Backdoors

Backdoors are software used to spread malware and prevent the malware from being detected by antivirus [13].

3. Worms

Worms are malware that copies the desired information and then distributes it over the network [13].

4. SpyWare

Spyware is a non-suspicious malware application that monitors users' confidential information, such as messages, contacts, bank authentication numbers, and user location. This information is immediately sent to the attackers who created the application[13].

C. Cybercrime

Terms such as cybercrime, computer crime, cloud crime, and computer misuse are things that refer to all criminal activities such as fraud, theft, extortion, forgery, and embezzlement related to the internet or computers, especially to access, transmit, or manipulate data illegally[14]. Cybercrime evolves from faulty applications or misuse of internet services. The concept of cybercrime is historical. Cybercrime is a new trend that is gradually growing along with the penetration of the internet into every sector of society, and no one can predict its future[14]. In general, cybercrime can be divided into two types of categories:

- a. Crimes that directly affect computer networks and devices. Examples are malicious code, computer viruses, and malware[14].
- b. Computer networks or devices facilitate crimes committed. Examples include cyber stalking, fraud and identity theft, phishing scams, and information warfare[14].

D. Android

Android is a platform created by a company called Android Incorporation. Google has acquired Android and launched the Android Open Source Project (AOSP). Android, a reasonably young platform, underwent a speedy development process, so in 2016, Android dominated the market with 84.1% of the existing market share[15]. The factors that cause Android to dominate are as follows:

- a. Android has a superior security platform compared to its competitors. Android combines features from the operating system, such as Unix User, Efficient shared memory, preemptive multitasking identifiers (UID), and file permissions using the JAVA programming language and libraries from its class. Even though Android itself is an application written in the JAVA programming language, Android uses its Virtual Machine rather than the JAVA standard.
- b. Android is used in various smartphone brands because the Android system itself can be easily changed according to the needs of smartphone manufacturers. Things that can be changed are not only the Android software itself, but the hardware can also be altered. In updating the version of Android, smartphone manufacturers can be directly involved in the development process so that Android itself can be better known and used by other manufacturers[16].

E. FjordPhantom

Android malware, such as FjordPhantom, attacks the banking sector, explicitly attacking banking applications to steal customer data. According to the Promon, this malware is spread via SMS, email, and other messaging applications[17]. In its distribution, this malware uses virtualization and then combines it with Android-based malware.

This malware was created using open-source sources and can be found on the GitHub platform. It uses virtualization because it allows application programs to run in virtual containers[17]. Another purpose of using virtual containers is to prevent malware from being detected by the device's security system without the user's knowledge[18].

Not only that, this malware also uses a hooking framework to carry out its attacks on banking applications[17]. Fake banking applications are created to accommodate genuine banking applications in a virtual container, which then uses a hooking framework to hook the API from the application and retrieve user data used to manipulate transactions[18], [19].

How FjordPhantom works

Fig. 1. FjordPhantom Illustration (adapted from [17])

F. Mobile Banking

Mobile Banking is a breakthrough in the banking world where technology has developed rapidly in this era. Along with the large number of smartphone users, the demand for mobile banking is increasing. It forces banks, microfinance institutions, software companies, and service providers to provide services that cover clients' needs. Mobile banking is believed to significantly impact the market because it makes all activities easier for users. According to Juniper Research, in 2017, more than 1 billion people used mobile banking, which was 15% of the total global mobile subscription base[20].

III. METHOD

This section will discuss the methods and data used by the author in this research.

A. Research Method

This research uses the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) method, which allows the author to collect and compile information from various sources. The SLR method can provide a detailed and comprehensive understanding of the author's topics. It can also be a reference and better study material for further research in this field or topic[21].

B. Research Step

In this research, the author uses literature studies from journals, articles, papers, and web pages sourced from the internet. The journals, articles, and papers were specifically sourced from Scopus and Google Scholar. The author also used Publish or Perish to facilitate the search process. Specific keywords enabled more targeted searches and refined the research scope. The following outlines the stages of the research:

Fig. 2. Research Step

C. Data Sources

The author used the Publish or Perish tool with Scopus and Google Scholar reference sources to narrow the search in this research. Apart from that, the author also used the Google search engine to search for other references that were not found in the publication. Table 1 shows that 22 publications were selected by the author, with details of 16 publications from journals, two from conferences, and four websites.

TABLE I. Journal, Article, Paper, Webpage Collected

Year	Journal	Conference	Webpage	Total (%)
2009	[7]	-	-	1 Publication (4.54%)
2012	[9]	-	-	1 Publication (4.54%)
2013	-	[10],[11]	-	2 Publication (9.09%)
2014	[2]	-	-	1 Publication (4.54%)
2015	[16],[20]	-	-	2 Publication (9.09%)
2016	[12]	-	-	1 Publication (4.54%)
2017	[3]	-	-	1 Publication (4.54%)
2018	[21]	-	-	1 Publication (4.54%)
2019	[22]	-	-	1 Publication (4.54%)
2020	[1],[8]	-	-	2 Publication (9.09%)
2021	-	-	[6]	1 Publication (4.54%)
2022	[14], [15]	-	-	2 Publication (9.09%)
2023	[4],[13],	-	-	2 Publication (9.09%)
2024	[5]	-	[17],[18],[19]	4 Publication (18.18%)
Total	16 Publication (72.72%)	2 Publication (9.09%)	4 Publication (18.18%)	22 Publication (100%)

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

After analyzing some of the information obtained, the author found that the FjordPhantom malware uses virtualization techniques and messaging platforms in its distribution, such as SMS, email, and others[17]. Hooking frameworks allow the FjordPhantom malware to take over the API function of the target application so that it can monitor and manipulate incoming data or information without the knowledge of the user or system[22]. With this method, FjordPhantom successfully bypasses the device's security system and becomes undetectable.

In the attack process, the FjordPhantom malware hosts the targeted banking application in a virtual container. In this case, virtualization techniques play a role in containing and running malicious code stored in virtual containers. In the execution process, when the user runs the application, it will run the application hosted in the virtual container. The malware will carry out its attack to steal the victim's bank account credentials and manipulate their transactions[17].

V. CONCLUSION

This research was carried out to find out the process and execution of the FjordPhantom malware, in which case the author can conclude that the FjordPhantom malware is malware that attacks banking applications and is only found on devices with the Android operating system. Android is an open-source operating system, making it more vulnerable to attack[13]. It makes Android devices easy targets for cybercriminals to slip or inject malware. FjordPhantom uses virtualization techniques, which allow the FjordPhantom malware to steal data without the knowledge of the user and system. The virtualization technique itself is a technique that can run several applications/tasks using a virtual container at the same time, so it is not easy to know/detect.

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